

THREE FUNCTIONS FOR MBK-OPEN SETS

Keskın Kaymakci A.

Selcuk University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Mathematics, 42130, Campus, Konya, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

In this study, we introduce a new family of functions called mbk-irresolute functions and give some characterizations of them. By introducing the mbk-continuous functions regarding mbk-open sets, some of its properties and equivalences are obtained. Besides, we present a new the concept of the graph of a function called a mbk-closed graph and investigate some of their basic properties.

Keywords: mbk-open sets, mbk-irresolute functions, mbk-continuous functions, mbk-closed graph functions.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

Let G be a subset of Z and (Z, ω) be a topological space (briefly, space). $G \subseteq Z$ is said to be open [4] iff $G \in \omega$. Complements of open sets are said to be closed. The interior of G (resp. closure of G) is denoted by $\text{int}(G)$ (resp. $\text{cl}(G)$). It is known that a subset G is said to be regular open (resp. regular closed) [5] if $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(G))$ (resp. $G = \text{cl}(\text{int}(G))$). The δ -interior of G [6] is consist of $H \subseteq G$ such that for every H is regular open and is denoted by $\delta\text{int}(G)$ and defined. A subset G is called δ -open if $G = \delta\text{int}(G)$. The collection of all δ -open sets is a topology on Z and denoted by ω^δ such that $\omega^\delta \subseteq \omega$. The complement of a δ -open is called δ -closed. Similarly, the δ -closure of G [5] is consist of $z \in Z$ such that $(J \cap G) \neq \emptyset$ for every J is regular closed neighborhood of $z \in Z$ and is denoted by $\delta\text{cl}(G)$.

Recall some necessary knowledges.

Definition 1.1. ([1]) Let (Z, ω) be a topological space and $G \subseteq Z$. Then G is said to be an mbk-open if $G \subseteq \text{clo}(\omega_\gamma\text{-int}(G)) \cup \text{int}(\omega_\gamma\text{-clo}(G))$.

The family of all mbk-open sets of Z will be denoted by $\text{MBKO}(Z)$.

Remark 1.2. ([1]) Although $\text{MBKO}(Z)$ is closed under arbitrary union but isn't closed under finite intersection. So, it doesn't form a topology.

Definition 1.3. ([2]) Let (Z, ω) be a topological space and $G \subseteq Z$. G is said to be a mbk-closed if $(Z-G)$ is a mbk-open set. $\text{mbk-cl}(G) = \bigcap \{T \subseteq Z: G \subseteq T, T \text{ is mbk-closed set}\}$ is said to be mbk-closure of G .

Lemma 1.4. ([2]) For $G \subseteq Z$ in (Z, ω) , then G is mbk-closed set iff $G = \text{mbk-cl}(G)$.

Definition 1.5. (Z, ω) is said to be

(1) mbk- T_0 -space [2] if for each $z_1, z_2 \in Z$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$ there exists a $P \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that either $z_1 \in P$ and $z_2 \notin P$ or $z_2 \in P$ and $z_1 \notin P$.

(2) mbk- T_1 -space [2] if for each $z_1, z_2 \in Z$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$ there exist $P, W \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z_1 \in P, z_2 \in W, z_2 \notin P$ and $z_1 \notin W$.

Definition 1.6. ([4]) (Z, ω) is said to be

(1) T_1 -space if for each $z_1, z_2 \in Z$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$ there exist $P, U \in \omega$ so that $z_1 \in P, z_2 \in W, z_2 \notin P$ and $z_1 \notin W$.

(2) T_2 -space if for each $z_1, z_2 \in Z$ when $z_1 \neq z_2$ there exist $P, W \in \omega$ so that $z_1 \in P, z_2 \in W$ and $(P \cap W) = \emptyset$.

The family of all closed sets of (X, τ) will be indicated by τ^1 . In this paper, we introduce three functions related to mbk-open sets. Besides, we obtain some properties of them.

2. MBK-IRRESOLUTE FUNCTIONS, MBK-CONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS AND MBK-CLOSED GRAPHS

In this section, firstly we introduce three notions which are mbk-irresolute functions, mbk-continuous functions and mbk-closed graph functions. Then, we obtain some fundamental properties.

Definition 2.1. For G be a subset of (Z, ω) , $\text{mbk-ker}(G) = \bigcap \{P \subseteq Z: P \in \text{MBKO}(Z), G \subseteq P\} \subseteq Z$ is called mbk-kernel of G .

Theorem 2.2. In any topological space (Z, ω) , $y \in \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\})$ iff $z \in \text{mbk-ker}(\{y\})$.

Proof. Sufficiency. Let $y \notin \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\})$. Then, there exists a $P \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z \in P$ and $y \notin P$. Therefore, $z \notin \text{mbk-ker}(\{y\})$.

Necessity. This proof is obtained similarly the proof of sufficiency.

Definition 2.3. A subset G of (Z, ω) is called an mbk-neighborhood of a point $z \in Z$ if there exists a $P \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z \in P \subseteq G$.

Theorem 2.4. For a subset G of (Z, ω) , then $\text{mbk-ker}(G) = \{z \in Z: \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset\}$.

Proof. Let $z \in \text{mbk-ker}(G)$ and assume that $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G = \emptyset$. So, $z \notin (Z - \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}))$ so that $(Z - \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\})) \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ and $G \subseteq (Z - \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}))$ from Definition 1.1. Since $z \in \text{mbk-ker}(G)$, this is impossible. Hence $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset$ and $\text{mbk-ker}(G) \subseteq \{z \in Z: \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset\}$.

Conversely, let $z \in Z$ and $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset$. Assume that $z \notin \text{mbk-ker}(G)$. Then there exists a $P \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $G \subseteq P$ and $z \notin P$. From hypothesis, let $y \in [\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G]$. Hence V is a mbk-neighborhood of y so that $z \notin V$. So, this is contradiction and $z \in \text{mbk-ker}(G)$. Hence, $\{z \in Z: \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset\} \subseteq \text{mbk-ker}(G)$.

Eventually, $\text{mbk-ker}(G) = \{z \in Z: \text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \cap G \neq \emptyset\}$ is hold.

Definition 2.5. A subset G of (Z, ω) is called an mbk-D-set if there are two mbk-open sets P and W such that $P \neq Z$ and $G = (P - W)$.

Proposition 2.6. Let (Z, ω) be a topological space and $z \in Z$. If a singleton $\{z\}$ is an mbk-D-set, then $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \neq Z$.

Proof. Since $\{z\}$ is an mbk-D-set of Z , there exist $P, W \in \text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $P \neq Z$ and $\{z\} = (P - W)$. Hence $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \subseteq P \neq Z$ and so $\text{mbk-ker}(\{z\}) \neq Z$.

Definition 2.7. $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is said to be a mbk-irresolute function if for each $z\in Z$ and each $V\in\text{MBKO}(X)(f(z)\in V)$, there is an $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)(z\in P)$ such that $f(P)\subseteq V$.

Theorem 2.8. If $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is an mbk-irresolute surjective function and $H\subseteq X$ is an mbk-D-set, $f^{-1}(H)\subseteq Z$ is an mbk-D-set.

Proof. Let $H\subseteq X$ be an mbk-D-set. So, there are $S,V\in\text{MBKO}(X)$ so that $S\neq X$ and $W=(S-V)$. As f is an mbk-irresolute, $f^{-1}(S),f^{-1}(V)\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ by using Definition 2.7. Since $S\neq Y$ and f is surjective, $f^{-1}(S)\neq Z$. So, $f^{-1}(H)=(f^{-1}(S)-f^{-1}(V))$ and $f^{-1}(H)\subseteq Z$ is an mbk-D-set.

Definition 2.9. A function $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is called an mbk-continuous function if $f^{-1}(S)\subseteq Z$ is an mbk-open set, for each $S\subseteq X$ is open.

Theorem 2.10. For a function $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$, the next properties are equivalent:

- (1) f is an mbk-continuous;
- (2) $f^{-1}(R)\subseteq Z$ is an mbk-closed, for each $R\in\varpi^t$;
- (3) $f(\text{mbk-cl}(G))\subseteq\text{cl}(f(G))$, for each $G\subseteq Z$;
- (4) $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(H))\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))$, for each $H\subseteq X$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) This proof is clear.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) Let $H\subseteq X$. Then, by using (3) $f(\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(H)))\subseteq\text{cl}(f(f^{-1}(H)))\subseteq\text{cl}(H)$. Therefore, $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(H))\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (3) Let $H=f(G)$, for $G\subseteq Z$. Then, from (4) $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(f(G)))\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(f(G)))$. Eventually, $f(\text{mbk-cl}(G))\subseteq\text{cl}(f(G))$.

(2) \Rightarrow (4) Let $H\subseteq X$. As $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))\subseteq Z$ is an mbk-closed, $f^{-1}(H)\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))$ by using Lemma 1.4. Therefore, $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(H))\subseteq\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H)))=f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))$ and $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(H))\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(H))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (2) Let $R\in\varpi^t$. Using (4), $\text{mbk-cl}(f^{-1}(R))\subseteq f^{-1}(\text{cl}(R))=f^{-1}(R)$. Then $f^{-1}(R)\subseteq Z$ is a mbk-closed and hence f is a mbk-continuous.

Definition 2.11. (Z,ω) is said to be mbk- T_2 -space if for each $z_1,z_2\in Z$ when $z_1\neq z_2$ there exist $P,W\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z_1\in P, z_2\in W$ and $(P\cap W)=\emptyset$.

Theorem 2.12. If $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is a mbk-continuous injective function and (X,ϖ) is T_2 -space, then (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_2 .

Proof. Let $z_1,z_2\in Z$ when $z_1\neq z_2$. According to hypothesis since f is injective $f(z_1),f(z_2)\in X$ so that $f(z_1)\neq f(z_2)$. Since (X,ϖ) is T_2 -space, using Definition 1.6(2) there exist $S,V\in\varpi$ so that $f(z_1)\in S, f(z_2)\in V$ and $S\cap V=\emptyset$. As f is a mbk-continuous function $f^{-1}(S), f^{-1}(V)\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z_1\in f^{-1}(S)$ and $z_2\in f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(S)\cap f^{-1}(V)=f^{-1}(S\cap V)=f^{-1}(\emptyset)=\emptyset$ and $f^{-1}(S\cap V)=\emptyset$. Hence, (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_2 from Definition 2.11.

Definition 2.13. For a function $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$, the graph $G(f)=\{(z,f(z)):z\in Z\}$ is called mbk-closed if for each $(z,x)\notin G(f)$, there exist a $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ and a $V\in\varpi$ so that $z\in P, x\in V$ and $(P\times V)\cap G(f)=\emptyset$.

Lemma 2.14. The function $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ has a mbk-closed graph iff for each $z\in Z$ and $x\in X$ when

$x\neq f(z)$ there exist a $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ and a $V\in\varpi$ so that $z\in P, x\in V$ and $f(P)\cap V=\emptyset$.

Theorem 2.15. If $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is an injective function with mbk-closed graph, then (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_1 .

Proof. Let $z_1,z_2\in Z$ when $z_1\neq z_2$. As f is injective, then $f(z_1)\neq f(z_2)$. Since f has a mbk-closed graph there exist a $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ and a $V\in\varpi$ such that $z_1\in P, f(z_2)\in V$ and $f(P)\cap V=\emptyset$. So, $z_2\notin P$ and hence (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_1 using Definition 1.5(2).

Theorem 2.16. If $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is an injective mbk-continuous function with mbk-closed graph, then (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_2 .

Proof. Let $z_1,z_2\in Z$ when $z_1\neq z_2$. As f is injective, then $f(z_1)\neq f(z_2)$ and $(z_1,f(z_2))\in[(Z\times Y)-G_f]$. Since the graph G_f is a mbk-closed, a $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ and a $V\in\varpi$ so that $z_1\in P, f(z_2)\in V$ and $f(P)\cap V=\emptyset$. As f is a mbk-continuous, $f^{-1}(V)\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ so that $z_2\in f^{-1}(V)$ and $P\cap f^{-1}(V)=\emptyset$. Therefore, (Z,ω) is a mbk- T_2 by using Definition 2.11.

Theorem 2.15. If $f:(Z,\omega)\rightarrow(X,\varpi)$ is a surjective function with mbk-closed graph, then (X,ϖ) is a T_1 -space.

Proof. Let $x_1,x_2\in X$ when $x_1\neq x_2$. Since f is surjective, there exists $z\in Z$ so that $f(z)=x_2$ and hence $(z,x_1)\notin G_f$. From Lemma 2.14, there exist a $P\in\text{MBKO}(Z)$ and a $V\in\varpi$ so that $z\in P, x_1\in V$ and $f(P)\cap V=\emptyset$. So, $f(z)=x_2\notin V$ and (X,ϖ) is a T_1 -space from Definition 1.6(1).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The notion of continuity is one of the most important subjects on topology. So, it is studied densely several authors. We focus on three functions which names are mbk-irresolute, mbk-continuous and mbk-closed graph for the concept of mbk-open sets. Besides, we introduce the concept of mbk-D-sets and obtain some properties related to it. Our future plan will focus on separation axioms by using mbk-D-sets. For them, we will examine these axioms under the three functions we focus on in this study.

References

1. Kaymakci, A.K., MbK-Open Sets, The 7th Mediterranean International Conference Of Pure And Applied Mathematics And Related Areas (MICOPAM 2024), 43-47.
2. Kaymakci, A.K., Three functions for mbk-open sets, submitted.
3. Kuratowski, K., Topology, Vol. I, Academic Press, New York, 1966.
4. Singal, M.K., Mathur, A., On nearly compact spaces, Boll. Un. Mat. Ital., Serie IV(4-6)(1969),702-710.
5. Stone, M. H., Application of the theory of Boolean rings to general topology, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., 41 (1937), 375-381.
6. Velićko, N. V., H-closed topological spaces, Amer. Math. Soc. Transl., 78 (1968), 103-118.